

Vulcanization of Natural Rubber : Influence of Hydrofuramide on Sulphenamide Acceleration System

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Influence of hydrofuramide (a reaction product of furfural and ammonia) on cure characteristics of sulphenamide accelerated sulphur vulcanization of natural rubber is reported. Presence of hydrofuramide causes a significant reduction in induction time, scorch time and optimum cure time though the overall cure rate and crosslink density do not increase. The effect of hydrofuramide on apparent energy of activation of vulcanization is negligible. The physical properties of the vulcanizate are also not affected by the presence of hydrofuramide. The sharp reduction in induction time in presence of hydrofuramide is attributed to reductive fission of sulphenamide by hydrogen sulphide (produced by the reaction of elemental sulphur with hydrofuramide).

INFLUENCE of hydrofuramide on thiuram vulcanization¹⁻⁴ and on thiazole⁵ acceleration system was reported earlier. The work is now extended to sulphenamide acceleration system.

Experimental

Method of preparation and analytical data of hydrofuramide, quality of natural rubber (NR) and other ingredients used in this work are the same as described earlier^{1,2,5}. The sulphenamide used in this study was CBS, (N-cyclohexyl benzthiazyl 2-sulphenamide).

Mixing and vulcanization : Mixing and vulcanization procedure has been described earlier^{1,2,5}. The vulcanization temperature in this work was 150°.

Rheometric study and energy of activation : Cure characteristics of the compounds were studied using Monsanto Rheometer (R100). The various cure parameters calculated from rheograph, e.g., t_{90} , t_{max} etc. have been defined earlier^{1,2,5}. The apparent energy of activation was calculated from the slope of the straight line plots of $\log t_{90}$ against reciprocal of absolute temperature^{6,7}.

Determination of free sulphur and combined sulphur : Free sulphur in the vulcanizate was determined by sodium sulphite method following the standard ASTM procedure⁸. Combined sulphur was determined from the acetone extracted vulcanizate¹ by zinc nitric acid process in accordance with the standard ASTM procedure⁸.

Determination of crosslink density and crosslink efficiency : Physical crosslink density of the vulcanizate was determined by equilibrium swelling

method using Flory Rehner's⁹ equation as described earlier^{1,2,7}.

Chemical crosslink density was computed using Mullins¹⁰ equation from physical crosslink density and elastic constant as described earlier^{4,7}. Crosslink efficiency was determined by dividing combined sulphur with chemical crosslink density⁷.

Results and Discussion

Rheometric study and energy of activation : The cure characteristics of gum vulcanizates containing varying levels of hydrofuramide are shown in Fig. 1, while the cure characteristics of HAF (N-330) black filled compound containing varying levels of hydrofuramide is shown in Fig. 2. The various parameters calculated from the rheographs are given in Table 1.

It can be observed from Fig. 1 and Table 1 that the incorporation of hydrofuramide slightly reduces the minimum viscosity of the compound. There is a significant reduction in induction time as well as scorch time with increasing level of hydrofuramide. Induction time is 6.8 min for the control compound (containing no hydrofuramide) while that for the compound containing 3 phr hydrofuramide is 1.84 min. There is also a reduction in optimum cure time with increasing levels of hydrofuramide.

However, it is interesting to note that although hydrofuramide causes a reduction in scorch and induction time, as well as in optimum cure time, the ultimate torque as well as cure rate is not increased by the presence of hydrofuramide.

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Fig. 1. Effect of hydrofuramide on cure characteristics of sulphenamido accelerated sulphur vulcanization system. Base formula : NR-100, ZnO-5, St. acid-2, CBS-0.8, S-2.5 hydrofuramide (HFA)-variable. Rheograph : Temp. 150°, Arc-3°.

Fig. 2. Effect of hydrofuramide on cure characteristics of sulphenamido accelerated sulphur vulcanization system. Base formula : NR-100, HAF-50, ZnO-5, St. acid-2, CBS-0.8, S-2.5, hydrofuramide (HFA) variable. Rheograph : Temp 150°, Arc-3°.

TABLE 1—PARAMETERS CALCULATED FROM RHEOGRAPHS (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2)

Rheograph	Fig. 1				Fig. 2			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Hydrofuramide (phr)	2	1	0.5	—	2	1	0.5	—
Minimum viscosity	3.7	4.2	4.7	6.9	4.6	4.7	5	6.7
Induction time (t_i) min.	1.84	2.90	5.20	6.80	1.25	2.0	2.70	3.70
Scorch time (t_s) min.	1.94	3.10	5.55	7.20	1.85	2.35	3.20	4.05
Opt. cure time (t_{oo}) min.	7.15	9.55	11.85	12.95	7.45	9.55	10.80	11.05
Max. cure (t_{max})	66.7	63.1	63.0	64.4	85.1	82.2	82.1	83.6
Cure rate index	19.19	15.50	15.87	17.89	16.39	13.89	13.16	14.29

The cure characteristics of the (N-330) black filled compound containing varying levels of hydrofuramide (Fig. 2) also follow the same trend as the gum compound—that is, incorporation of hydrofuramide reduces the induction time, scorch time and optimum cure time. There is no significant improvement in cure rate as well as t_{max} with incorporation of hydrofuramide. The Arrhenius plots of gum compounds containing varying levels of hydrofuramide is shown in Fig. 3. The plots of $\log t_{oo}$ against reciprocal of absolute temperature follow a straight line pattern suggesting

that Arrhenius equation holds good in the range studied. The apparent energy of activation, E (calculated from the slopes of the above straight line plots), is indicated on the graphs. It is apparent from Fig. 3 that incorporation of hydrofuramide causes no reduction in E value. All the four plots (control compound and three compounds containing 0.5 phr, 1 phr and 2 phr of hydrofuramide) are almost parallel. This suggests that hydrofuramide, although it shortens induction time and scorch time, does not activate (or promote) the overall vulcanization reaction of natural rubber accelerated by sulphenamide.

The apparent energy of activation of N-330 (HAF) filled compound containing varying level of hydrofuramide is given in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Effect of hydrofuramide on energy of activation in sulphenamide accelerated sulphur vulcanization system.

Base formula : NR-100, ZnO-5, St. acid-3, CBS-0.8, S-2.5. Arrhenius plots:
 ○—No hydrofu amide △—0.5 phr hydrofuramide
 □—1 phr hydrofuramide ◇—2 phr hydrofuramide

TABLE-2

Compound	E Kcal/mole
Control (No hydrofuramide)	18.57
Compound containing 0.5 phr hydrofuramide	18.75
Compound containing 1 phr hydrofuramide	18.75
Compound containing 2 phr hydrofuramide	18.35

Thus in the case of black filled compounds also, incorporation of hydrofuramide causes no reduction in apparent energy of activation. The sharp decrease in induction period as well as scorch time due to the incorporation of hydrofuramide can be explained as follows. In sulphenamide system the period of induction and scorch time depends on the amine group attached to the thiazole to give the corresponding sulphenamide accelerator. In the sulphenamide acceleration system the actual accelerator precursor is the amine salt of MBT.

As suggested by Scheele and coworkers^{1,2} the amine salt of MBT is the first product of sulphenamide formed which then reacts rapidly with the zinc oxide or zinc soap to give an amine addition complex which is the active accelerator leading to activation of elemental sulphur.

The ease of formation of amine salt of MBT from the sulphenamide would decide the length of induction period in sulphenamide accelerated vulcanization system. Since incorporation of hydrofuramide causes a significant reduction in induction

time and scorch time, hydrofuramide evidently promotes the decomposition of sulphenamides. The mode of action of hydrofuramide to facilitate the decomposition of sulphenamides could probably be due to reductive fission of S-S and/or S-N bonds by hydrogen sulphide with elemental sulphur as shown below

Formation of H₂S by interaction of sulphur with hydrofuramide has been reported earlier³.

The incorporation of hydrofuramide, though promotes the decomposition of sulphenamides (as shown above), does not increase the cure rate significantly, neither there is a reduction in apparent energy of activation. This suggests that it does not promote the rate determining step of sulphenamide accelerated sulphur vulcanization of natural rubber.

Thus hydrofuramide, being a weaker base compared to cyclohexylamine (produced from CBS—the sulphenamide studied here) seems to have insignificant effect on the overall cure rate.

Crosslink density. The crosslink density (determined by equilibrium swelling method) of gum compound containing varying levels of hydrofuramide is shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that all the curves attain a maxima beyond which crosslink

Fig. 4. Variation of crosslink density as a function of cure time. Base formula: NR-100, ZnO-5, St acid-2, CBS-0.5, S-2.5.
 ○—No hydrofuramide Δ—0.5 phr hydrofuramide
 □—1 phr hydrofuramide ⊙—2 phr hydrofuramide

density decreases due to the well known phenomena of reversion. At the early stage of cure, the crosslink density is higher with compounds containing hydrofuramide as compared to the control compound. However, the maximum crosslink density is not significantly improved by the incorporation of hydrofuramide. Thus ultimate crosslink density is not influenced by the presence of hydrofuramide. These observations are in agreement with rheometric study where t_{max} is not improved by the incorporation of hydrofuramide although torque at the early stage of cure is higher with compounds containing hydrofuramide.

Free sulphur and crosslink efficiency: The rate of consumption of sulphur with time was determined by measuring free sulphur in the vulcanizate as a function of cure time. The plot of free sulphur content vs time of cure of gum compounds is shown in Fig. 5. Initially the rate of consumption of elemental sulphur is higher with compounds containing hydrofuramide. This is because the hydrofuramide promotes the decomposition of sulphenamides and hence vulcanization starts earlier.

Fig. 5. Free sulphur as a function of cure time. Base formula NR-100, ZnO 5, St acid-2, CBS-0.5, S-2.5.
 ○—0 phr hydrofuramide Δ—0.5 phr hydrofuramide
 □—1 phr hydrofuramide ⊙—2 phr hydrofuramide

The consumption of sulphur apparently follows a first order rate law up to 20 min of cure time beyond which the plots follow a straight line pattern almost parallel to X-axis.

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The efficiency of crosslinking was determined from the chemical crosslink density and combined sulphur as described earlier. In the early stage of cure although crosslinking efficiency was slightly higher with compounds containing hydrofuramide the efficiency at the optimum cure appears to be the same in all cases as can be seen from Table 3.

Compound	Efficiency of vulcanisation
Control compound	15.0
Compound containing 0.5 phr hydrofuramide	15.6
Compound containing 1.0 phr hydrofuramide	15.0
Compound containing 2.0 phr hydrofuramide	14.8

Physical properties : The physical properties of gum compounds as well as N-330 (HAF) black filled compounds containing varying levels of hydrofuramide are shown in Tables 4 and 5. It can be observed from the tables that with the incorporation of hydrofuramide, tensile strength and ultimate

TABLE 4—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF GUM VULCANIZATES

Base formula : NR-100 ; ZnO-5 ; Stearic acid-2 ; OBS-0.8 ; S-2.5 ; Hydrofuramide-variable

Compound	1	2	3	4
Hydrofuramide (phr)	—	0.5	4.0	2.0
Tensile strength N/mm ²	22.5	22.6	23.8	22.8
Elongation at break %	650.0	660.0	660.0	675.0
8.0% Modulus N/mm ²	4.1	4.1	4.9	4.9
Hardness (IRHD)	45.0	45.5	46.5	46.5

elongation increases to some extent, whereas beyond 0.5 phr hydrofuramide 300% modulus decreases marginally with increasing levels of hydrofuramide.

TABLE 5—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF HAF (N-330) FILLED VULCANIZATE

Base formula : NR-100 ; HAF-50 ; ZnO-5 ; Stearic acid-2 ; OBS-0.8 ; S-2.5 ; Hydrofuramide-variable

Compound	5	6	7	8
Hydrofuramide (phr)	—	0.5	1.0	2.0
Tensile strength N/mm ²	24.0	24.2	21.4	24.5
Elongation at break %	450.0	450.0	460.0	475.0
800% Modulus N/mm ²	16.5	16.5	16.2	16.0
Hardness (IRHD)	73.5	73.5	74.5	75.0

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